

VOCATIONAL GUIDANCE IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Abstract. *The essence of vocational guidance as a social problem is manifested in the need to overcome the contradiction between the objectively existing needs of society in a balanced structure of personnel and the inadequate subjective professional aspirations of young people.*

Keywords: *vocational guidance, school, college, education, training, preparation, plan, program.*

In order to form the knowledge and skills of school students, educate them in the spirit of devotion to national and universal values, increase the authority of the teaching profession and the quality of teachers, improve textbooks and educational and methodological complexes based on modern requirements, build modern models of public education institutions that meet international standards, as well as in accordance with the State Program for the Implementation of the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 in the “Year of Ensuring Human Interests and Development of the Mahalla”: increasing the responsibility of teachers for the education and training of young people, their exactingness in their continuous professional development others [1].

“The vocational guidance system at the present stage of its development is designed to ensure coordination of the actions of state bodies, schools, families, bodies of vocational, secondary specialized, higher education and other social institutions involved in its implementation, continuous and timely resolution of scientific and organizational issues related to career guidance, a comprehensive design of career guidance impacts on the student's personality, taking into account the socio-economic forecast” [10;4].

The concept of "vocational guidance" seems understandable to anyone who gets acquainted with it even for the first time - this is the orientation of schoolchildren to certain professions. Approximately the same definitions are given in methodological manuals, where vocational guidance is seen as helping young people choose a profession. In addition, vocational guidance is often understood as a system of activities that help a person entering life, scientifically sound choice of a profession or a system of educational work in order to develop a professional orientation, help students in moments of professional self-determination.

Therefore, before giving one general definition of vocational guidance, let us clarify our understanding of its three main components: “activity”, “profession”, “orientation”.

“In the philosophical encyclopedic dictionary, activity is defined as a specifically human form of an active relationship to the surrounding world, the content of which is its expedient change and transformation. The introduction of the category “activity” into the considered concept of “vocational guidance” makes it possible to present career guidance not only as a practice, but also as a theoretical activity, or rather, an interdisciplinary scientific direction, which is not only a certain amount of knowledge, but also an activity to obtain this knowledge” [3; 14].

Having arisen as a practical activity, vocational guidance is gradually enriched with theory, which makes it possible to consider vocational guidance in the unity of theoretical and practical activities.

“Profession (from the Latin *professio* - an officially indicated occupation, specialty, from *profiteor* - I declare my business) - a kind of labor activity, occupations that require certain training and are a source of livelihood” (TSB 2nd edition - M., 1955, V.35, - p. 164).

The concept of "guidance" is used in a number of sciences. And everywhere it is somehow connected with the determination of the location and with the choice of the direction of movement. In the encyclopedia, orientation (fr. *orientation* literally - to direct to the east) is defined in the literal and figurative sense, in the literal sense - the ability to understand the environment, in the figurative sense - the direction of scientific, social and other activities in a certain direction.

Whatever definitions are given to the concept of "career guidance", it is clear that they are all related to the activity of choosing a profession. If a young person is trying to navigate the world of professions and begins to actively find out how this or that particular profession corresponds to his life aspirations, then in this case it is better to talk about his orientation towards the profession. If he becomes the object of pedagogical or other influence in order to choose a profession suitable for him and for society, then it is better to talk about orientation in the sense of orienting him to the profession. The latter expresses the essence of the matter more precisely. However, in practice there is a tradition to talk about orientation in both senses.

As already mentioned, one of the tasks of the educational process for schoolchildren in grades 1-4, according to the Federal State Educational Standard, is to prepare students for a conscious choice of a profession. Qualitative knowledge about activities should be given in an accessible format. At the same time, it is important to take into account age-related characteristics: avoid importunity and present information in adequate forms (games, watching themed cartoons, children's books, and so on). Already in grade 1, the class teacher should introduce children to the professions of those who work at school. For example, the program of the subject "The world around us" involves an excursion, during which the children will find out what a cook, a nurse, a librarian and technical staff do. The goals of early vocational guidance for schoolchildren in grades 1-4: to expand the initial ideas about the place of work in the life of every person; detail the basic concepts of different professions; provide an opportunity for immersion in various activities through games and other methods. High-quality career guidance work in primary school allows you to solve the following tasks: to cultivate a respectful attitude towards people engaged in physical labor, as well as towards all professions without exception; to form an understanding of the importance of work for a person; to acquaint with a variety of modern activities; teach you to do your job well; motivate to study and work through the use of cognitive and career guidance methods; to develop the creative abilities of the child in the course of acquaintance with professions. [2].

The lack of a unified point of view on the concept of career guidance is also explained by other reasons. For example, the fact that this is a complex problem, and therefore approaches to its definition may be different. If vocational guidance is viewed through the prism of pedagogical practice, which proceeds under the predominant influence of school teachers, masters of training and production plants, etc., then the adoption of this point of view as the only and main one creates a pedagogical image of vocational guidance.

“If you look at this process through the prism of psychological science, then psychological concepts and concepts that explain the features of a particular choice will come to the fore. Within the framework of this approach, an appropriate image of career guidance is formed as a psychological phenomenon, consisting of two interrelated aspects:

a) students making decisions about their professional choice;

b) influencing the student's psyche in order to form professional intentions, to make such a choice of profession that would correspond to the interests and abilities of the individual and at the same time would be in line with social needs” [5; 27].

“The third approach is sociological. At the same time, the process of professional orientation is considered as part of a more general process of social orientation of young people. Accordingly, the choice of a profession is considered as an act determined by the general life orientation, the desire of the individual to take a certain place in the social structure of society, in a social group” [6; 28].

This implies the need for an interdisciplinary approach both in understanding the essence of career guidance and in practical work to guide young people to certain professions.

The above understanding of vocational guidance as a unity of practical work and theory allows us to give the following definition. Career guidance is “a purposeful activity to prepare young people for a reasonable choice of a profession in accordance with personal inclinations, interests, abilities, and at the same time with social needs for personnel of certain professions and different skill levels. It represents the unity of practical activity and developing interdisciplinary theory and is realized not only in the educational process of working with students” [10; 28].

The beginning of vocational guidance is often attributed to 1908, to the time of the opening of the first vocational counseling bureau in Boston (USA). However, according to another point of view, vocational guidance appeared much earlier, in ancient times. Career guidance arose from the needs of the development of human society, and therefore, like society, it has its own history and prehistory. Naturally, vocational guidance could not appear before professions appeared, and, consequently, the need for orientation to these professions.

The history of the emergence of some elements of assessing a person's professional suitability goes back to the depths of centuries. This applies mainly to the diagnosis of knowledge, skills and abilities. Already in the middle of the III millennium BC. in ancient Babylon, they conducted tests of school graduates who trained scribes. Thanks to the extensive knowledge of those times, the professionally trained scribe was the central figure of the Mesopotamian civilization; he knew how to measure fields, divide property, sing, play musical instruments. During the tests, they tested his ability to understand fabrics, metals, plants, as well as knowledge of all four arithmetic operations.

In the III millennium BC. in China, there was a widespread position and profession of a government official. Accordingly, the first elements of professional selection for this position appeared here. The ceremony was noticeably facilitated by the atmosphere of solemnity and splendor around young people who dared to take state examinations for this position. These examinations in Chinese society were perceived almost as a festival. The emperor himself often gave the topic of the exam, he also conducted a direct test of knowledge at the final stage of the multi-stage competitive selection of applicants.

Other examples give us the ancient history of Sparta, Athens, Rome. In Sparta, a system for the education of warriors was created and successfully implemented, in Rome - a system for the selection and training of gladiators.

There is a lot of data similar to the above, and all of them point to a rather early period of the emergence of elements of what is now commonly called professional diagnostics and professional selection. If we proceed from the now widespread point of view about the inclusion

of vocational diagnostics and vocational selection in the system of vocational guidance, then we can say that vocational guidance arose a long time ago.

However, if we now look at vocational guidance as a social process, which includes not only the above-mentioned vocational diagnostics and vocational selection (selection), but also vocational education, vocational consultation, social and vocational guidance and vocational education, then it becomes clear that vocational guidance as a scientifically meaningful human activity could appear only later, from the time when the trend of differentiation and integration of individual sciences began to gain strength. Consequently, the above historical data should be considered as an indication not of the history, but of the prehistory of the emergence of career guidance. The story began much later, during the period of a radical breakdown of the social under the pressure of the development of a large-scale machine industry, i.e. in the period of developed capitalism with its inevitable companions - an increase in the intensity of production processes, an increase in the role of specialization and professionalization of labor, as well as the forced need to carry out professional training for huge masses of workers.

It was at this time that the practical need was determined to attract labor, train it and distribute it to various labor operations in accordance with individual differences and abilities of people.

In January 1908, in Boston, as noted above, the first youth career guidance bureau began to work to assist adolescents in determining their career path. The activities of this bureau are considered to be the beginning of career guidance. Then a similar bureau was established in New York. His tasks included studying the requirements for a person by various professions, more lethal knowledge of the abilities of schoolchildren. The bureau conducted its work in contact with teachers, using tests and questionnaires. The experience of these bureaus began to spread widely in the USA, Spain, Finland, Switzerland, Czechoslovakia and other countries.

In its work, the bureau was guided by the following provisions:

in terms of importance, the choice of profession can be equated with the choice of marriage;

it is better to choose a profession than to hope for a good chance;

no one should choose a profession without careful consideration, without relying on a professional consultant;

young people should get acquainted with a large number of professions, and not immediately take on a “convenient” or accidentally turned up job;

the choice of a profession proceeds the more successfully, the more carefully the professional consultant studies the characteristics of the personality of the person choosing, the factors of a successful choice and the world of professions.

In the US, more emphasis was placed on professional selection. The director of the psychological laboratory at Harvard University, Professor G. Munsterberg. He can be called the founder of psychotechnics.

By order of a telephone campaign, he studied the suitability of candidates for the profession of a telephone operator. At that time, the telephone operator had to make up to 150 connections per hour, that is, every 10 s. it was necessary to connect subscribers, and for this it was necessary to perform 14 separate psychophysical acts. Many telephone operators could not stand such a load and quit their jobs. This was unprofitable for entrepreneurs. Therefore, it became necessary to develop recommendations for the professional selection of candidates for telephone operators

according to their psychophysiological qualities. As a result, staff turnover has dropped dramatically.

The First World War (1914-1918) caused a further expansion of the need for determining professional suitability: it required accelerated training of persons with the intellectual and physical qualities necessary for military affairs.

The intensive technical re-equipment of the industry of the leading capitalist states, the development of fundamentally new technology at the beginning of the 20th century, including military technology, actualized the problem of “man-technology”. It became more and more acute to realize that not everyone can manage a complex technical device - this requires knowledge, abilities and appropriate skills. The war significantly sharpened interest in the issues of correlating human abilities with the requirements of professions. Thus, the ground was prepared for the development of scientific research work on test methods for assessing personality. In the United States, the first version of the so-called group test was created, which made it possible to quickly assess the suitability of conscripts for military service in various branches of the armed forces. The created test was considered as a psychological weapon, so all tests, the scale of research and their results were kept secret. On the basis of research, “unfit persons” were expelled, those incapable of service were assigned to “black work”, staffing of non-commissioned officers and officer schools, equalization of units according to the level of intelligence, recruitment into special units, etc.

As can be seen from history, life itself led to the emergence of career guidance as a practice, and as a result, interdisciplinary scientific knowledge. [10], [6].

The goals and objectives of vocational guidance are successfully implemented to the full extent when vocational guidance itself can rely on a developed theory and methodology. And it is no coincidence: after all, concepts, ideas, views, ideas, forms, methods and principles are refracted and tested in theory and methodology, which make it possible to increase the efficiency of practical work.

So, career guidance is “a scientifically based system of preparing young people for a free and independent choice of a profession, designed to take into account both the individual characteristics of each individual and the need for a full distribution of labor resources in the interests of society” [13;23]. Career guidance should be a unity of practice and interdisciplinary theory. At the same time, theory is of great importance: after all, it is in it that certain ideas are refracted, which then help to turn practical work into scientific and practical work. Theory does not appear, as a rule, together with the activity itself, in order to formulate a theory that contributes to the improvement of career guidance practice. In vocational guidance, practical work was usually put at the forefront to orient students mainly to working professions. Much later, attention was paid to the need to develop a theory, and only relatively recently, the need to develop methodological issues of vocational guidance began to be felt.

“The practical side includes the activities of state and public organizations, enterprises, institutions, schools, and families to improve the process of professional and social self-determination in the interests of the individual and society as a whole” [8; 28].

The theory of career guidance can be defined as follows: “it is a set of statements that reflect in a concentrated form a set of views, ideas and ideas aimed at the implementation of effective career guidance” [11; 28].

This definition is relatively simple and general: although it is useful for “entering the world of theory, but from the point of view of scientific rigor, it is inevitable and in determining the theory of any activity. A deeper definition of the following concept is as follows: “the theory of vocational guidance is a form of scientific organization of scientific knowledge, which gives a holistic view of the patterns and essential connections of two processes - professional self-determination of young people in accordance with personal interests, inclinations, abilities and orientation to those professions for which there is a public need for personnel” [13; 28].

Let's consider the main components of the theory of vocational guidance for schoolchildren: facts, patterns, principles. There are few reliable facts obtained with the help of scientific methods in career guidance. Therefore, one of the important tasks is to collect new facts and give them a correct interpretation. This turns out to be important in cases where the search for new facts is carried out with the help of one or more hypotheses. The latter also form an important part of the theory. For example, each district (region) may have its own specific factors influencing the choice of a particular profession. The hypothesis about such possible factors helps to create research methods that allow us to evaluate the phenomenon of interest and, on this basis, develop practical recommendations for improving career guidance work with students.

An important component of the career guidance theory is certain regularities. The search for them serves as a common goal of scientific activity. Knowledge of regularities is, ultimately, the most important thing for which scientific research is usually undertaken. The found regularities are usually expressed with the help of the conceptual apparatus and the specific language of science, which is distinguished by greater accuracy, expressiveness, and greater opportunities for joining career guidance with the concepts of other sciences, including mathematics.

The level of development of each theory is often determined by the composition and quality of the principles underlying the activity. A lot of attention is paid to the formulation of career guidance principles. However, it cannot be said that the development of a system of career guidance principles has been completed: much remains to be done to create a coherent, consistent system that meets all requirements.

Since the object of career guidance is the process of social and professional self-determination of a person, it is important first of all to formulate a group of principles that guide (or should guide) girls and boys when choosing their profession and place in the social structure of society.

“The principle of conscientiousness in choosing a profession is expressed in the desire to satisfy not only personal needs in labor activity, but also to bring as much benefit to society as possible.

The principle of compliance of the chosen profession with the interests, inclinations, abilities of the individual and at the same time the needs of society in the personnel of a certain profession expresses the connection between the personal and social aspects of choosing a profession. By analogy with a well-known thought, one cannot live in society and be free from society - one can also say: one cannot choose a profession based only on one's own interests and without considering the interests of society. Violation of the principle of matching the needs of the individual and society leads to an imbalance in the professional structure of personnel.

The principle of activity in choosing a profession characterizes the type of personality activity in the process of professional self-determination. You have to actively search for a profession yourself. In this, a big role is called upon to play: a practical test of the strength of the

students themselves in the process of labor and vocational training, advice from parents and their professional experience, searching and reading (on a topic of interest) literature, work during practice, and much more.

The last principle in this group is the principle of development. This principle reflects the idea of choosing a profession that would give the individual the opportunity to improve their skills, increase earnings, as experience and professional skills grow, the opportunity to actively participate in public work, satisfy the cultural needs of the individual, the need for housing, recreation, etc.” [14; 29-30]

“There is a group of principles in vocational guidance that are closely related (and in many respects intersect) with general pedagogical principles. These are the following principles:

The relationship of career guidance with life, work, practice, providing assistance to a person in choosing his future profession in organic unity with the needs of the national economy in qualified personnel.

The connection of vocational guidance with the labor preparation of schoolchildren is a principle that provides for a good formulation of labor education and training. In isolation from labor training, vocational guidance acquires the features of abstractness, invocation, isolation from practice, from the general tasks of the labor and professional development of the individual;

Systematic and continuity in vocational guidance is ensured by vocational guidance work from grades 1 to 11, subject to the mandatory continuity of this work from grade to grade the relationship of the school, family, basic enterprise, secondary vocational schools and the public in the career guidance of students provides for close contact to help young people choose a profession. At the same time, it is supposed to strengthen the focus and coordination in joint activities;

The nurturing nature of vocational guidance lies in the need to carry out vocational guidance work in accordance with the tasks of forming a harmonious personality, in the unity of labor. Economic moral, aesthetic, legal and physical education;

the relationship between diagnostic and educational approaches to career guidance work is a principle that presupposes the inadmissibility of opposing one approach to another. Each of them solves its own problems.

a differentiated and individual approach to students, depending on the age and level of formation of their professional interests, on differences in value orientations and life plans, on the level of academic performance. Differentiation of students by groups allows you to more accurately determine their means of influence, which, being effective in one group, may be ineffective in another. Differentiation creates conditions for the implementation of an individual approach;

the optimal combination of mass, group and individual forms of vocational guidance work with students and their parents, affirming the need to use different forms, moving away from the traditionally used mass forms alone, increasing attention to a balanced combination of all forms of work;

the correspondence of the content of the forms and methods of career guidance to the needs of the professional development of the individual and, at the same time, the needs of the district (city, region) in personnel of certain professions and the required level of qualification” [16; 32].

Thus, there are many definitions of this concept and this happened as a result of the development of career guidance activities. Indeed, over time, the requirements changed, and with

them changed their content and concept. The term “career guidance” develops as the society's understanding of the goals, objectives, methods, forms and, in general, the essence of career guidance changes. Each of them reflects certain aspects of vocational guidance, highlights a function, indicates the practical or theoretical level of its development, considers the participation of the family as a social and educational institution from the standpoint of pedagogy, psychology, management theory, as a social and educational institution, emphasizes the duality of vocational guidance as a problem public and pedagogical.

Vocational guidance is a national in scale, economic in terms of results, social in content, pedagogical in terms of methods, a complex multifaceted problem.

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